

Effect of wind turbine blade waste on cement hydration and gel structure: Competitive interaction of glass and polyester resin

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Wind turbine blade waste
Alkali dissolution
Hydration process
NMR
XCT

ABSTRACT

With the rapid expansion of wind energy infrastructure, managing wind turbine blade waste (WTBW) has become an increasing environmental concern. This study explores the potential use of WTBW as a partial cement replacement to understand its influence on the reaction process, reaction products, and gel structure of cementitious composites. The alkali dissolution behavior of WTBW was investigated under different pH conditions, while isothermal calorimetry was used to monitor early hydration. The gel structure was characterized using ²⁹Si and ²⁷Al Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR), and the resulting pore morphology and microstructure was visualized using X-ray Computed Tomography (XCT). Results revealed a critical competing mechanism between the glass and resin components of waste. At 5 wt% replacement, the glass content contributed to the release of Si(OH)₄ and Al(OH)₄ species, promoting a more complex and extended C-(A)-S-H gel network and improved pore structure. However, the polyester resin in WTBW hindered early hydration beyond 5 wt% by consuming hydroxide ions, reducing pore solution pH, and releasing inhibitory glycol and carboxylate salts. In contrast, the pozzolanic activity of glass promotes gel formation, potentially offsetting the negative effects of the resin and offering a long-term performance enhancement.

1. Introduction

The rapid growth of wind energy has led to a significant increase in wind turbine construction, making the disposal of wind turbine blade waste (WTBW) a major concern for the coming decade [1]. Globally, various methods have been developed to manage WTBW, but landfilling remains a prevalent solution [2]. Utilizing WTBW in cementitious materials offers a promising alternative, as it can be incorporated as a supplementary cementitious material (SCM), potentially reducing the need for cement [3,4]. This approach not only helps lower material costs but also contributes to CO₂ reduction. However, the use of WTBW as an SCM is still underexplored, and understanding its effects on cement hydration and the properties of hardened concrete is crucial for advancing this solution.

As mentioned, research has already explored the exciting possibility of incorporating WTBW into cement/concrete mixes [5,6]. This approach offers significant potential for construction applications because of WTBW composition. Specifically, its rich content of calcium

(Ca), silicon (Si), and aluminum (Al) makes it an ideal candidate, which are the major reactive components in cementitious materials [3]. Whether used as fiber [7], aggregates [8,9], or fine powders [4], WTBW presents a high-value opportunity to be repurposed directly into concrete structures. Focusing on its fibrous nature, research has primarily explored the potential of WTBW as a fiber reinforcement in cementitious composites. Duan et al. [10] investigates the use of recycled wind turbine blade fibers (RWTBF) as reinforcement in mortar. Adding 2 vol % of the fibers yields significant cost benefits: the normalized cost for compressive strength is slightly reduced by 2.16 % and, more notably, the cost for flexural strength is reduced by 8.84 %. These savings confirm the RWTBF-reinforced mortar standing as an economical construction material with promising market viability in the wind power and building sectors. Menna et al. [11] discusses the reuse of recovered fibers from WTBW in fiber-reinforced mortar and concrete and evaluates the sustainability and economic potential of the recycled WTBW fibers. The bending strength of mortar specimens showed improvements of around 16 % with 2 wt% of WTBW fibers, also tensile strength of concrete

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2025.113273>

Received 14 October 2025; Received in revised form 13 November 2025; Accepted 27 November 2025

Available online 29 November 2025

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specimens showed up to a 13.28 % increase with 2.5 wt% of WTBW fibers. Both the observed increase in flexural and bending strength suggests that using WTBW as fiber reinforcement is highly promising for enhancing the performance of cement and concrete mixes. Beyond using WTBW fibers for reinforcement, researchers have also explored repurposing the bulk material of WTBW as a substitute for conventional fine and coarse aggregate in cementitious composites. Rodin et al. [12] explored using shredded and sieved WTBW as a sand replacement, dividing the material into three fibrous grades and one powdery grade. It is important to note these fibrous components, used here as aggregate, were much larger than those typically used for reinforcement. Incorporating the fibrous WTBW actually led to increased or equivalent 7-day flexural strength compared to control specimens. However, replacing sand with powdery material proved detrimental, resulting in a 30 % reduction in flexural strength. Yazdanbakhsh et al. [9] investigated using shredded, needle-like WTBW (plain and grooved) to replace 5 wt % and 10 wt % of coarse aggregate (CA) in concrete. At these low replacement rates, the compressive strength was successfully retained. Similarly, 3-point bending tests showed that the inclusion of the WTBW aggregate led to only a minimal reduction (around 5–7 %) in the material flexural strength compared to the control mix. Despite some positive or negligible effects at low dosages, the overall trend in utilizing WTBW as an aggregate replacement typically shows a generalized decrease in both the compressive and flexural strength of the cementitious mix.

Given the mixed results of using WTBW for reinforcement or aggregate, the most compelling application is as a direct cement replacement, capitalizing on its residual pozzolanic activity. This approach is doubly beneficial for reducing cement consumption and its associated CO₂ emissions while providing a sustainable solution for managing the growing volume of wind energy composite waste [4,5]. This strategy supports broader sustainability goals in the construction industry, particularly by promoting waste valorization and improving resource efficiency [11,13–15]. Manso-Morato et al. [13] studied the environmental impacts of managing WTBW into concrete through life cycle assessment (LCA). The mechanical recycling of WTBW was combined with concrete production by using WTBW as an aggregate replacement (2 %, 5 %, and 10 % vol) to create fiber-reinforced concrete, despite yielding lower environmental impacts (e.g., –28.3 % global warming potential and –5.9 % abiotic depletion potential for fossil fuels) compared to incineration. WTBW, mainly composed of glass fibers and resin, shows promise as an SCM due to the reactive nature of its glass phase and its potential as a stable filler [16]. The glass component, rich in silica and alumina, can dissolve under alkaline conditions and participate in cementitious reactions, potentially contributing to the formation of C–(A)–S–H type gels [17]. In contrast, the resin portion—commonly epoxy or polyester [18]—may behave differently under high-pH environments, where degradation byproducts could interfere with hydration, especially at early stages [3]. Liu et al. [7] reported that epoxy resin-based WTBW delayed the hydration process of cementitious materials, leading to a prolonged setting time. This was due to the epoxy resin undergoing a slight degradation in a high pH environment. The alkalis were partially consumed by epoxy resin instead of cement particles. As reported by Yousef et al. [19], the polyester-based WTBW embedded in a cement matrix undergoes a similar degradation process. Microscopy images clearly demonstrated the substantial contribution of the alkaline solution to the decomposition of the remaining polyester resin on the surface of WTBW. Ismail et al. [20] reported that the ester group (C=O) from polyester in an alkaline environment will transform to glycol group (OH and C–H) and carboxylate group (COO[–]) (as shown in Eq. (1)). This degradation phenomenon may also happen in cementitious materials with WTBW incorporation. Building on visual evidence of WTBW degradation by microscopy, an alkali dissolution test is a promising way to be conducted to quantify the release of reactive silicate and aluminate species from

WTBW. The results of this test helped examine the delaying effects on the hydration process and evaluate the solidification of different phases related to hydration heat release [21]. Nikolić et al. [22] used different alkali solutions (different pH) to dissolve slag to investigate the leaching of Si and Al. Results showed that a higher pH leads to faster dissolution of Si and Al. The Si dissolution can be explained by the surface charge mechanism: when the surface charge is electrically neutral (at low pH), the number of positively and negatively charged surface complexes is equal. In a high pH environment, however, the surface becomes more negatively charged. This is because the number of more reactive ≡ Si–O[–] complexes increase due to the ionization of ≡ Si–OH groups, which weakens the Si–O–Si structure and thus enhances Si dissolution. To discuss it further, Liu et al. [3] reported that while the glass promotes beneficial gel-forming species such as Si(OH)₄ and Al(OH)₄, (Al can also be another forms like Al₂O(OH)O₆^{2–}, and AlO₆^{3–} [23] but still can contribute to hydration in cement, as shown in Eq. (2) and Eq. (3)) the resin tends to consume hydroxide ions and reduce pH, thereby slowing hydration. To confirm the distinct effects of the glass and resin components on the cementitious hydration process, alkali dissolution of elements and heat release should be jointly examined to elucidate their reaction behavior. In addition, the current understanding of the mutual influence between the organic and inorganic parts of WTBW in a cementitious matrix is limited. Since both components interact with alkalis as mentioned, there may be an underlying competition mechanism that remains unexplored. Specifically, previous studies have often treated WTBW as a uniform filler, and the incompatible nature of its two primary components was overlooked that the reactive glass phase which promotes strength, and the organic polyester resin which can hinder gel growth. These insights will form the basis for further investigation into how the organic and inorganic constituents of WTBW affect hydration behavior, gel structure, and the overall performance of cement-based composites.

Expanding on the understanding of the effect of WTBW on cement hydration products, particularly gel structure, NMR is a widely used method to identify the Si and Al coordination states in cementitious systems [24,25]. As mentioned previously, the glass part of WTBW contributes to the release of silicate and aluminate species under an alkaline environment [3]. Liu et al. [26] characterized raw WTBW powder using NMR, showing its silicate state is dominated by Q³/Q⁴. The complex silicate composition of WTBW powder suggests it will be difficult to dissolve in alkaline solutions and will have low pozzolanic activity. With limited calcium availability, the dissolved silica promotes the formation of longer silicate chains in the hydrated gels. At the same time, the higher Q³/Q⁴ silicate states enhance the three-dimensional gel structure, which highly depends on the chemistry of the raw materials [27,28]. The presence of aluminum also enhances cross-linking, leading to a more complex and three-dimensional C–A–S–H gel structure [29,30]. However, the resin components may compete with the glass for alkalis in the pore solution, lowering pH and hindering the dissolution of reactive species. As a result, the WTBW content plays a critical role in determining the balance between inhibition and enhancement in gel formation. To date, no studies have systematically reported the chemical influence of WTBW on gel structure in cementitious systems. This remains an unexplored area, and it is important to clarify this mechanism. This work will be the first to employ advanced solid-state ²⁹Si and ²⁷Al MAS NMR spectroscopy to precisely track this competition. And the unique contribution is providing atomic-level evidence of the organic-inorganic interference, showing the resin-induced depolymerization (reduction of mean chain length) of the C(N)–A–S–H gel via

carboxylate-calcium interactions. Ultimately, the C(N)-A-S-H gel structure strongly influences the microstructure and determines the mechanical performance of the composite matrix.

With the reaction mechanism and gel structure clarified, the next step is to evaluate the micro- and macro-level consequences, such as pore structure (micro) and mechanical strength (macro), which are critical for the practical performance of cementitious composites [3,31]. Previous studies have shown that the structure of C-(A)-S-H gels, particularly their chain length and cross-linking density, can influence pore morphology and refine the capillary pore network in cement-based materials [29,32]. Pan et al. [32] incorporated a high volume of glass powder into a cement system, and their results showed that the mean chain length (MCL) of gels and capillary pores increased considerably due to extra Si from the glass powder. To further characterize pore size distribution and matrix texture, mercury intrusion porosimetry (MIP) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) are widely used techniques [33,34]. He et al. [33] used MIP to characterize the pore size distribution of SCM-incorporated ultra-high-performance fiber-reinforced concrete. Their findings showed that the SCM contributed to refining the microstructure, with a 30 wt% slag replacement confirmed by the MIP test. Additionally, SEM confirmed that the SCM contributed to a dense interfacial transition zone (ITZ) between the fiber and matrix. However, MIP and SEM have limitations in capturing the full three-dimensional nature of the pore network, and X-ray computed tomography (XCT) allows for a non-destructive and spatially resolved assessment of pore distribution and geometry, offering a more comprehensive understanding of how internal structure evolves when waste materials are introduced [35]. Simultaneously, inner pores can also be precisely measured and detected by XCT, a capability that MIP and SEM do not fully offer [36]. WTBW is a complex and heterogeneous material due to its composite nature. The core challenge is the strong bond between the fibers and the resin matrix [3]. Therefore, the WTBW is not a uniform substance, and the shredded waste is reprocessed into a new non-homogeneous material. As a result, the further ground of shredded WTBW remains a heterogeneous material. The non-homogeneous powder can influence the microstructure development of the cementitious matrix [37]. To address the complexity and heterogeneity of WTBW, it is crucial to establish a more mechanistic link between its microstructural features and macro-scale performance via a visible and precise illustration, and XCT can assist in evaluating the pore development influenced by WTBW.

The objective of this study is to investigate the influence of wind turbine blade waste (WTBW) powder as a cement replacement material in terms of reaction process, gel structure, and performance of the resulting matrix. An experimental plan with alkali dissolution tests and isothermal calorimetry was developed to (i) assess the release of silicate and aluminate species, and (ii) examine WTBW effect on the early cement hydration process, respectively. The reaction products of the paste were analyzed using X-ray diffraction (XRD), thermogravimetry (TG), and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), while the gel structure was characterized by nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR). Microstructural development was further examined using X-ray computed tomography (XCT). In addition, compressive strength tests were carried out to evaluate the mechanical performance of the samples. The combined results were used to understand the influence of WTBW on the hydration process and gel structure, particularly the main chain length of the gels, and to provide insight into how inorganic and organic components interact within a cementitious environment.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials and sample preparations

The ground WTBW powder sourced from Denmark (Eldan recycling) was employed in this experiment. CEM I 52.5 R was also sourced from Denmark (Aalborg Portland) and was used as a binder for a rapid

hydration reaction. The detailed characterization of cement and WTBW is presented in Section 3.1. The paste mix design of the control sample and WTBW-containing samples is listed in Table 1.

2.2. Testing methods

2.2.1. XRF

Raw WTBW or cement powder was finely ground for homogeneity, then analyzed by X-ray fluorescence (XRF). For XRF analysis, 1 g of ground sample was mixed with 10 g of flux (99.5 % Lithium Tetraborate and 0.5 % Lithium Iodide). This mixture was fused in a platinum or platinum-gold crucible at 950–1100 °C for 25 min to form a molten solution. The molten mixture was then poured into a preheated mold, solidifying into a fused glass bead for XRF spectrometer (LeNeo Fluxer) analysis.

2.2.2. XRD

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis of cement, WTBW, and WTBW-containing paste samples was performed using an X'Pert PRO instrument (Co-K α radiation, 40 kV, 30 mA). Paste samples were crushed (around 70 μ m) by agate mortar and pestle, immersed in 2-propanol for 24 h to halt hydration, and then dried at 40 °C for 24 h. All samples were scanned from 10 to 70° 2 θ , with a step size of 0.05° and a 1-s counting time per step.

2.2.3. PSD

The particle size distribution (PSD) of the WTBW and cement was determined using laser diffraction analysis (Malvern Mastersizer 2000). Before measurement, the WTBW and cement samples were dried, and compressed air was used to break apart particle clusters for dry analysis. The particle size distribution was measured using a laser diffraction particle size analyzer.

2.2.4. TGA

Thermogravimetry analysis (TGA) tests were performed on \approx 40 mg crushed, powdered paste samples by using an STA 449 F1 instrument at a heating rate of 10 °C/min. Experiments were carried out from 40 °C to 1000 °C, in which N₂ was used as the carrier gas. The same hydration stoppage treatment was performed before the test as well.

2.2.5. FTIR

Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis was performed using a Varian 670-IR spectrometer with a wavelength range of 400–4000 cm⁻¹ with a resolution of 1 cm⁻¹. The powdered raw material and crushed paste samples were prepared following the same procedure as discussed above, after the hydration stoppage treatment.

2.2.5.1. Alkali dissolution test. WTBW was ground down and the mean particle diameter size was $d_{50} = 25 \mu$ m. The alkali dissolution test was performed as described in the literature [22]. Leaching of powdered WTBW was carried out by mixing the powder with NaOH solutions with

Table 1
Mix design of cement paste samples.

Sample ID	Cement	Powdered WTBW	Water	Note
Ref	100	/	40	Control sample
W2.5	97.5	2.5	40	2.5 wt% of cement replaced by WTBW
W5	95	5	40	5 wt% of cement replaced by WTBW
W7.5	92.5	7.5	40	7.5 wt% of cement replaced by WTBW
W15	85	15	40	15 wt% of cement replaced by WTBW

Water to cement mass ratio is 0.4.

concentrations of 0.01, 0.1, and 1 M, in a liquid to solid (L/S) ratio of 40 ml/g up to 90 days. Literature [38] indicates that the pH of a cement pore solution typically falls within the range of 12.5–13.9, depending on cement type. However, the incorporation of materials WTBW, which contains components that consume alkalinity, may probably lower the pH below the minimum literature value of 12.5. Therefore, using the 0.01 M solution (pH approx. 12) allowed us to model the entire expected spectrum of alkalinity, from the high initial pH (using 1 M NaOH) down to the lower. The dissolution process was carried out in a 500 ml plastic bottle and the slurry was placed on a shaking table with a constant speed of 200 rpm at room temperature (20 °C). The leaching slurry was extracted at regular intervals after 10 min, 1 h, 6 h, 1 day, 3 days, 7 days, 10 days, 14 days, 21 days, 28 days, and 90 days, then filtered. Leachates were analyzed for Ca, Si, Al, and Mg concentration by inductively coupled plasma emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES).

2.2.5.2. Isothermal calorimeter. Using the mixture proportions from Table 1, an isothermal calorimeter (I-Cal Flex) measured the heat evolution of the WTBW-containing pastes. We then analyzed the cumulative heat release and hydration exothermal rate to understand the hydration process of the WTBW fiber-reinforced cement matrix.

2.2.6. XCT

A ZEISS Xradia 520 Versa scanner was employed to perform X-ray Computed Tomography (XCT) on 28-day mortar cubic specimens (25 × 25 × 25 mm³). Five specimens, each one representing a separate mix-design (Table 1), were used to perform X-ray imaging. The beam energy was set at 140 kV (10 W). A high-energy filter was used to optimize the X-ray beam transmission. The entire specimen volume was captured. Thus, the scan field-of-view (FOV) was equal to 36.43 × 36.43 mm, while the corresponding pixel size was 35.6 μm. The exposure time was 1.5 s, and the bin size was set to 2.0. In total, 1601 projections were acquired per scan. Image reconstruction was performed by applying the filter back-projection. The acquired 16-bit image data was converted to 8-bit and thus reducing the computational cost. Avizo (ThermoFisher Scientific) was used for data visualization, phase segmentation, and corresponding data processing and quantitative analysis. Porosity behavior was investigated in each system, including measurements about pore size and spatial distribution, and shape factors.

2.2.7. NMR

Solid-state MAS NMR spectra were measured with a 14.05 T AVANCE IIIHD spectrometer (Bruker, DE) with operating frequencies of $\nu_{29\text{Si}} = 119.2$ MHz and $\nu_{27\text{Al}} = 156.4$ MHz. The spectrometer was equipped with a 4 mm broadband CP/MAS probe (Bruker, DE). 100–150 mg of material were loaded into 4 mm o.d. PSZ rotors and tightly closed with a Kel-F cap. ²⁹Si MAS spectra were measured using direct excitation with a 3.85 μs 90° excitation pulse, an interscan delay of 20 s and high-power ($\nu_{\text{dec}} = 100$ kHz) ¹H SPINAL64 decoupling during acquisition. ²⁷Al MAS spectra were measured using direct excitation with a 0.7 μs 15° excitation pulse, an interscan delay of 1 s and high-power ($\nu_{\text{dec}} = 100$ kHz) ¹H SPINAL64 decoupling during acquisition. All spectra were measured at 298K with $\nu_{\text{rot}} = 5$ kHz. Chemical shifts are reported relative to TMS ($\delta_{\text{iso}} = 0.0$ ppm) and 1 M Al(NO₃)₃ ($\delta_{\text{iso}} = 0.0$ ppm) for ²⁹Si and ²⁷Al, respectively.

The deconvolution of the ²⁹Si MAS NMR spectra was carried out using Origin 2024 Pro. The multiplex fit was used to calculate the area of each peak of silicon and aluminum state that exists in the spectra with a Lorentz function according to the literature [39]. The cumulative integrated percentage of each silicon and aluminum in AASW was obtained to calculate the mean chain length (MCL) and Al–Si substitution of C(N)–A–S–H.

²⁹Si MAS NMR has revealed important information regarding C(N)–A–S–H formation in the hydrated matrix. Resonances from the Q¹, Q², and Q²(1Al) sites, which constitute the silicate chains in the C–A–S–H

gel, have been seen using ²⁹Si MAS NMR [40]. The mean chain length (MCL) of non-crosslinked C(N)–A–S–H gel can be calculated by using equation (1), while the MCL of crosslinked C(N)–A–S–H gel can be calculated by using equation (2). The Al–Si substitution in the tetrahedral chains can be obtained from the intensities of the Q¹, Q², and Q²(1Al) resonances (equation (3)), as reported by Richardson et al. [41].

$$\text{MCL}_{\text{nc}} = \frac{2 \left[Q^1 + Q^2 + \frac{3}{2} Q^2(1\text{Al}) \right]}{Q^1} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{MCL}_{\text{c}} = \frac{4 \left[Q^1 + Q^2 + Q^2(1\text{Al}) + Q^3 + 2Q^3(1\text{Al}) \right]}{Q^1} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\text{Al}[\text{IV}]}{\text{Si}} = \frac{\frac{1}{2} Q^2(1\text{Al})}{Q^1 + Q^2 + Q^2(1\text{Al})} \quad (6)$$

2.2.7.1. Compressive strength. Following a 28-day curing period at 20 °C and 95 % relative humidity, compressive strength testing was conducted on the paste cubic (25 × 25 × 25 mm³) by EN 196-1 [42]. The testing involved applying a constant loading rate of 2400 N/s until the fracture load was reached.

3. Results

3.1. Characterization of raw materials

3.1.1. Basic characterization

The chemical composition of WTBW and cement was determined using XRF, as summarized in Table 2. WTBW mainly consists of SiO₂ (38.73 wt%), Al₂O₃ (8.91 wt%), and CaO (12.60 wt%), while cement has a significantly higher CaO content (64.16 wt%) and a lower SiO₂ content (19.32 wt%). The loss on ignition (LOI) of WTBW (33.5 wt%) is substantially higher than that of cement (2.53 wt%), likely due to the decomposition of organic resin components in WTBW. The presence of MgO (4.62 wt%) and TiO₂ (0.28 wt%) in WTBW suggests the inclusion of filler materials in the composite structure of the blades [43].

The XRD patterns of cement and WTBW, shown in Fig. 1(a), indicate distinct mineralogical compositions. The cement primarily contains alite (C₃S), calcite, and brownmillerite, while WTBW exhibits peaks associated with quartz (from glass fiber) and calcite (from the filler) in the blade [43].

The particle size distribution (PSD) results in Fig. 1(b) show that WTBW particles are generally coarser than cement. The cumulative particle size curve indicates that cement has a finer distribution, with a median particle size of 14.8 μm, whereas WTBW has a broader distribution with larger particles of 23.6 μm.

TGA results in Fig. 1(c) further confirm the presence of polyester resin in WTBW. Three distinct weight loss peaks are observed, corresponding to thermal decomposition of the polyester resin components [44]. In contrast, cement shows weight loss behavior associated with a small content of free water (40–105 °C) [45], gypsum (150 °C) [46] and carbonate decomposition (550–750 °C) [34].

FTIR spectra (Fig. 1(d)) reveal the presence of organic functional groups in WTBW, including C–H (2928, 1456, and 722 cm⁻¹) and C=O (1712 cm⁻¹) stretching vibrations, which are from the polyester resin. Typically, the C=O (1712 cm⁻¹) stretching is from the ester groups in the backbone [47,48]. The Si–O–Si and Si–O–T bands observed in WTBW suggest that the material retains silicate structures of glass fiber [44,47], which may contribute to its reactivity in the cementitious matrix.

3.1.2. Alkali dissolution

The alkaline dissolution behavior of Si, Al, Ca, and Mg from WTBW powder in NaOH solutions of varying concentrations (1 M, 0.1 M, and 0.01 M) is presented in Fig. 2(a)–(d). Additionally, the pH evolution over time is shown in Fig. 2(e).

Table 2

Raw materials compositions (unit: wt. %).

Group	Na ₂ O	MgO	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	SO ₃	K ₂ O	CaO	TiO ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃	Others	LOI ^a
WTBW	0.35	4.62	8.91	38.73	0.45	/	12.60	0.28	0.36	0.21	33.5
Cement	0.29	0.93	5.27	19.32	3.56	0.33	64.16	/	3.25	0.44	2.53

^a LOI = Loss on ignition at 950 °C.**Fig. 1.** Characterization of cement and WTBW (a) XRD; (b) PSD; (c) TGA and DTG; (d) FTIR.

As shown in Fig. 2(a), Si concentration increased gradually over time in all solutions, with the highest release observed in 1 M NaOH. After 90 days, Si concentration reached approximately 1000 mg/L in 1 M NaOH, while in 0.1 M and 0.01 M NaOH, the concentrations were significantly lower. Al leaching (Fig. 2(b)) followed a similar trend, with a notable increase over time, especially in the 1 M NaOH solution. The Al concentration remained below 50 mg/L in the 0.01 M NaOH solution at 90 days, indicating that a stronger alkaline environment promotes the dissolution of Al-containing phases in WTBW powder. In contrast to Si and Al, the Ca concentration (Fig. 2(c)) showed an initial increase followed by a decline, particularly in the 1 M NaOH solution, where it peaked at around 6 h and then dropped significantly after 3 days. This suggests that Ca initially dissolves but later participates as Ca(OH)₂ in an alkaline environment. In 0.1 M and 0.01 M NaOH, Ca dissolution was relatively stable over time, remaining below 10 mg/L. The Mg concentration (Fig. 2(d)) also showed an initial increase, peaking at around 10 days before stabilizing or slightly decreasing, particularly in the weaker NaOH solutions.

Fig. 2(e) illustrates the pH variations during the alkaline dissolution process. The initial pH values of the 1 M, 0.1 M, and 0.01 M NaOH

solutions were 13.74, 12.56, and 11.6, respectively. Over time, the pH remained relatively stable for 1 M NaOH but exhibited slight fluctuations in 0.1 M and 0.01 M NaOH solutions. The observed pH trends suggest that highly alkaline conditions facilitate the continuous dissolution of Si and Al, while Ca and Mg leaching are more influenced by early-stage dissolution and subsequent precipitation reactions. Overall, these results indicate that WTBW powder releases significant amounts of Si and Al under strong alkaline conditions, while Ca and Mg exhibit different dissolution-precipitation behaviors depending on the pH of the solution, which means the precipitation of secondary phases Ca(OH)₂, possibly hydrotalcite.

3.2. Reaction process

The heat flow, cumulative heat release, time to reaction peak (TTRP), and height of peak (HOP), initial and final setting time during the hydration of the different samples are illustrated in Fig. 3, which provides insight into the thermal behavior and kinetics of the reaction.

Fig. 3(a) illustrates the normalized heat flow curves of cement pastes with varying levels of WTBW powder replacement. The primary

Fig. 2. Alkaline dissolution of the WTBW until 90 days.

hydration peak appears between 10 and 20 h for all mixtures, with a slightly delayed peak observed as the WTBW powder content increases. The zoomed-in graph shows an obvious decrease in the normalized heat flow as the replacement level increases. This suggests that higher WTBW content slows the hydration process due to the presence of polyester resin in WTBW. The functional group of polyester resin (ester bonds) can react with hydroxide ions (forming glycol and carboxylate salts) in the pore solution, leading to a loss of pH during the reaction process [49]. Consequently, the reaction process is delayed by the higher content of

WTBW participation.

The cumulative heat release over time is shown in Fig. 3(b). The total heat release decreases gradually with increasing WTBW replacement levels, indicating reduced degree of hydration. The zooms in on the cumulative heat values after 150 h, showing a more pronounced reduction for W7.5 and W15 compared to the reference sample. This trend proves that the partial substitution of cement with WTBW powder impacts the hydration kinetics negatively. One key reason for this reduction is the dilution effect [50]: When cement is replaced by WTBW,

Fig. 3. Calorimeter data with (a) Normalized heat flow; (b) Normalized total heat release; (c) Time to reaction peak (TTRP) and height of peak (HOP); (d) Initial and final setting time.

the total amount of reactive clinker phases available for hydration decreases, leading to lower formation of hydration products. Since the resin content in WTBW does not contribute to cementitious reactions, its presence further lowers the effective binder content in the system. This reduction in cement dosage limits the availability of calcium ions, which are essential for the formation of C-S-H and other hydrates, thereby reducing the cumulative heat release and delaying the overall hydration process.

Fig. 3(c) presents the time to reach the reaction peak (TTRP) and the normalized height of the main hydration peak (HOP). As the replacement level rises, TTRP increases from 11.77 h for the reference to 13.76 h for W15. Meanwhile, HOP decreases significantly, reflecting reduced hydration intensity due to the dilution effect and lower reactivity of WTBW powder compared to cement. It is worth mentioning that W2.5 shows the fastest TTRP among the samples. Maybe very small amounts of WTBW absorb some free water in the pore solution leading to a localized lower W/C ratio. Subsequently, it results in a lower TTRP, indicating a faster hydration process than reference sample.

Setting times for each mixture are displayed in Fig. 3(d), which is according to literature [51]. Both initial and final setting times increase with higher WTBW powder content. The initial setting time ranges from 1.97 h for the reference to 2.53 h for W15, while the final setting time increases from 11.77 h to 13.76 h. These findings are in line with the observed reduction in hydration heat, indicating a retarding effect of WTBW powder (influence of polyester resin) on cement setting.

3.3. Reaction products

3.3.1. XRD

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the pastes are presented in Fig. 4, illustrating the crystalline phase composition at 28 curing days. The samples consist of varying ratios of WTBW. The identified phases, indexed in the figure, include portlandite (00-004-0733), calcite

Fig. 4. XRD of the pastes at 28 days.

(CaCO₃) (01-080-9776), alite (C3S) (Ca₃SiO₅) (00-055-0739), dolomite (CaMg(CO₃)₂) (00-005-0622), ettringite (Ca₆Al₂(SO₄)₃(OH)₁₂·26H₂O) (00-041-1451), quartz (SiO₂) (01-085-0795), gypsum (CaSO₄·2H₂O) (00-006-0046), and hemicarboaluminate (Ca₈Al₄CO₁₆·22H₂O) (00-041-0221).

In the reference sample, a prominent peak corresponding to portlandite is observed, indicating the typical hydration product of Portland cement. As the WTBW powder content increases from W2.5 to W15, a gradual reduction in the intensity of portlandite peaks is noted. This reduction may suggest a dual mechanism. First, the dilution effect caused by the lower overall Ca(OH)₂ content in the blended cement, and second, the consumption of portlandite due to the pozzolanic reaction. As we know from the alkaline dissolution test that the glass component of WTBW releases reactive silicate and aluminate species over time in a high pH environment. This reactive release may drive the Ca(OH)₂ consumption, leading to the formation of additional C-S-H and C-A-S-H phases, thus reinforcing the microstructure, particularly at later curing ages. Also, a slight increase in the hemicarboaluminate peak intensity is observed at higher WTBW levels, potentially due to more availability of reactive aluminates from WTBW as well. The ettringite peaks show similar intensity with different dosages of WTBW, suggesting that WTBW powder may not influence the formation of ettringite.

3.3.2. FTIR

The FTIR spectra of cementitious composites incorporating different amounts of WTBW powder are shown in Fig. 5. Several characteristic peaks were observed, indicating changes in the chemical composition and functional groups due to the incorporation of WTBW.

A broad peak around 970–976 cm⁻¹ was detected in all samples, corresponding to the asymmetric stretching of Si–O–Si bonds, a typical feature of C–S–H gel [52]. This peak slightly shifted with increasing WTBW content, suggesting potential interactions between WTBW-derived silica and the cementitious matrix. This is also due to the pozzolanic reactivity of the glass part from the WTBW. The Si–O–T (T = Si, Al) bending vibration at approximately 830–843 cm⁻¹ remained visible [53], which indicates the participation of the reactive aluminate species from the WTBW in the hydration process. This participation leads directly to the formation of the aluminosilicate structures, specifically the C–A–S–H gel network, which is a key phase for enhancing the long-term performance and densification of the hydrated system.

The presence of carbonate-related bands at 1430–1440 cm⁻¹ is associated with calcite in the hydrated pastes [54]. Also, given that calcite serves as a filler in the wind turbine blade structure [43], the incorporation of WTBW into the cement system results in the

Fig. 5. FTIR of pastes at 28 days.

characteristic peaks of calcite being observed in the FTIR analysis. The bands at 2340–2344 cm⁻¹ suggest carbonation reactions within the matrix, likely due to atmospheric CO₂ reacting with calcium-based phases [55]. The intensity of these peaks was similar across the samples, indicating that carbonation was not significantly affected by the WTBW addition. Additionally, the peaks observed in the range of 2950–2974 cm⁻¹ correspond to C–H stretching vibrations [47], which can be attributed to residual organic components from the polyester resin in WTBW.

The FTIR results confirm the retention of key cementitious phases in the presence of WTBW, while the minor shifts in Si–O–Si stretching suggest some interaction between WTBW-derived components and the C–S–H structure. The presence of residual organic signals further supports the incomplete decomposition of polyester resin, aligning with the thermal analysis observations.

3.3.3. TGA

Fig. 6 show the thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and its derivative (DTG) curves of cement pastes with varying levels of WTBW replacement at 28 days.

In Fig. 6(a), the weight loss profile indicates the decomposition of different phases in the cement pastes. The weight loss observed between 150 °C and 200 °C is attributed to the decomposition of the bound water of C–S–H and ettringite [56], which is present in all mixtures, including the WTBW-containing samples. The temperature range between 250 °C and 400 °C corresponds to the loss of polyester resin (major thermal

Fig. 6. (a) TG and (b) DTG of pastes at 28 days.

decomposition) [44] from the WTBW, and this is evident in the TGA curves of the WTBW samples (W2.5, W5, W7.5, and W15). As the WTBW content increases, a more noticeable weight loss in this region is observed, confirming the contribution of the polyester resin from the WTBW in the mixture. Furthermore, the calcite decomposition peak, located around 700 °C [34], is observed in all samples, with no significant changes across the different blends. Table 3 presents the relative mass loss of major phases.

Fig. 6(b) presents the derivative weight loss (DTG) curves, which allow for a more precise analysis of the thermal events. The peaks corresponding to the decomposition of polyester resin from the WTBW are clearer in the WTBW-containing samples, particularly for W7.5 and W15, where the loss is more significant. The peaks for the bound water of C–S–H and free water are also visible in all samples between 100 °C and 200 °C, with no significant differences observed between the reference and WTBW samples. The calcite and portlandite decomposition events are observed around 450 °C and 700 °C, respectively, with similar intensities across all samples, indicating that the presence of WTBW does not significantly impact the calcite and portlandite contents. TGA and DTG results indicate that the incorporation of WTBW increases the weight loss related to polyester resin decomposition, while the other phases, such as ettringite, calcite, and portlandite, remain relatively unaffected by the WTBW replacement. This indicates that WTBW substitution primarily changes the organic content of the mix without significantly changing the mineralogical composition.

3.4. Gel structure

3.4.1. ^{29}Si MAS NMR

The ^{29}Si MAS NMR spectra of raw cement and WTBW are presented in Fig. 7, with the corresponding deconvoluted peak positions and integrals summarized in Table 4. The cement spectrum (Fig. 7(a)) exhibits characteristic Q^0 peaks from Alite and Belite at approximately -69 to -72.8 ppm, confirming the presence of unreacted silicate phases [57]. The integral values indicate that a significant portion of silicon in cement exists in these isolated Q^0 units. In contrast, the WTBW spectrum (Fig. 7(b)) displays a broader distribution of peaks, with signals corresponding to Q^1 (-84.2 ppm), Q^2 (-90.9 ppm), Q^3 (-97.2 ppm), and Q^4 (-102.5 ppm). The dominance of Q^2 (41.1 %) and Q^3 (23.0 %) suggests a partially polymerized silicate network, likely originating from the glass fiber phase in WTBW [58]. The presence of Q^4 sites (6.9 %) further confirms the existence of highly cross-linked silicate structures in the quartz.

Fig. 8 presents the ^{29}Si MAS NMR spectra of the reference cementitious system and WTBW-containing composites, while the corresponding deconvoluted peak positions and integrals are summarized in Table 5. The left alignment number is the silicate sites after hydration, and the center alignment number is the silicate sites from raw materials in Table 5. Fig. 9 shows the summary of silicate site changes from hydration products and the summary of MCL changes. Compared to the reference (Fig. 8(a)), the WTBW-modified samples (Fig. 8(b)–(e)) exhibit noticeable changes in the silicate structure, indicating alterations in the reaction products.

The reference sample primarily contains Q^0 sites from Alite and Belite (-69 to -72.8 ppm), along with Q^1 (-78.6 ppm) and Q^2 (-81.9

Table 3
Relative mass loss of different phases.

	Relative mass loss in TG (wt. %)		
	Ettringite	Polyester resin	Calcite
Ref	2.01251	/	2.67727
W2.5	1.88827	3.27966	2.92488
W5	1.81217	3.59964	3.50177
W7.5	1.85527	3.91764	3.7828
W15	2.01865	5.01102	4.06457

ppm) species, characteristic of partially polymerized calcium silicate hydrate (C–S–H). As the WTBW content increases, the intensity of Q^0 peaks decreases, while the proportion of higher-order silicate species (Q^2 and Q^3) rises, suggesting an increased degree of silicate polymerization.

In WTBW-containing composites, additional peaks corresponding to WTBW-derived silica networks appear, including Q^1 (-84.2 ppm), Q^2 (-90.9 ppm), and Q^3 (-95.8 to -98.5 ppm). These signals are associated with the glass fiber phase of WTBW, indicating its partial dissolution and incorporation into the cementitious matrix. The presence of Q^4 species (-102.5 to -107.3 ppm) in WTBW composites, absent in the reference, suggests the formation of highly polymerized silicate structures, likely influenced by the interaction between WTBW and the alkaline cement pore solution. Moreover, peaks associated with aluminum-substituted silicate species ($Q^2(1Al)$ at -79.4 ppm and $Q^3(1Al)$ at -94.8 ppm) become more prominent with increasing WTBW content. This indicates possible Al incorporation into the C–S–H structure. The NMR results confirm that WTBW alters the silicate polymerization degree in the hydrated system. The reduction of Q^1 signals and the formation of Q^2 , Q^3 , and Q^4 species highlight the role of WTBW as a reactive component that contributes to structural modifications in the cementitious matrix.

Table 5 (with right alignment numbers) and Fig. 9 also summarizes the mean chain length (MCL) of the C–(A)–S–H gel in both non-crosslinked and crosslinked forms, along with the degree of Al–Si substitution. The reference system exhibits a relatively short silicate chain length (MCLnc = 3.8, MCLc = 7.4) and a low Al–Si substitution (0.104), indicating a typical C–S–H structure with limited polymerization.

With the incorporation of WTBW, the silicate chain length increases, particularly in the W5 sample, which shows the highest values (MCLnc = 7.0, MCLc = 14.7). This suggests enhanced polymerization, likely due to the reactive silica from the WTBW interacting with the cementitious matrix. The corresponding Al–Si substitution (0.356) also reaches its peak in W5, indicating substantial Al incorporation into the C–(A)–S–H gel.

However, at higher WTBW levels (W7.5 and W15), the MCL decreases, with W15 exhibiting even shorter chain lengths than the reference. This reduction suggests potential disruption in gel connectivity, possibly due to excessive unreacted WTBW particles acting as physical fillers rather than contributing to further silicate polymerization. The lower Al–Si substitution (0.081) in W15 further supports this, indicating limited Al incorporation at high WTBW dosages.

These findings align with the ^{29}Si NMR results, where WTBW initially promotes silicate polymerization but may hinder gel development when present in excess. This highlights the importance of optimizing WTBW content to balance reactivity and microstructural integrity in the hydrated system.

3.4.2. ^{27}Al MAS NMR

Fig. 10 and Table 6 present the ^{27}Al MAS NMR spectra of cement and WTBW, highlighting their distinct aluminum coordination environments. In cement, the dominant signal at 82.5 ppm corresponds to Al(IV)-2, indicating the presence of tetrahedrally coordinated aluminum, which is essential for C–(A)–S–H gel formation. The broad signal at 10.9 ppm is attributed to Al(VI)-1, representing octahedrally coordinated aluminum from unhydrated clinker phases.

In contrast, WTBW exhibits a more complex Al distribution, with multiple tetrahedral sites (Al(IV)-3 at 57.6 ppm and Al(IV)-4 at 88 ppm), suggesting the presence of aluminosilicate phases within the waste material. The Al(V) and Al(VI) sites in WTBW appear at 26.5 ppm and 11.8 ppm, respectively, though their intensity is lower compared to cement. This variation indicates that WTBW contains a mix of aluminum environments, which could influence its reactivity in the cementitious system.

These results suggest that the Al species in WTBW could contribute to the formation of C–(A)–S–H gels through partial dissolution and

Fig. 7. ²⁹Si MAS NMR of raw materials (a) cement; (b) WTBW.

Table 4
²⁹Si MAS NMR of raw materials.

Si site	Cement		WTBW	
	Pos. ^a	Inter. ^b	Pos.	Inter.
Q ⁴			-102.5	6.9
Q ³			-97.2	23.0
Q ²			-90.9	41.1
Q ¹			-84.2	29.0
Q ⁰	-72.8	45.4		
Q ⁰	-70.8	31.2		
Q ⁰	-69	23.4		

^a Pos. = Position (ppm).

^b Inter. = Integral (%).

reprecipitation, potentially enhancing the gel structure when incorporated at optimal levels. However, the presence of stable Al(IV) sites in WTBW also implies a degree of inertness, which may limit its full

Table 5

²⁹Si MAS NMR of paste samples and mean chain length and Al-Si substitution of C-A-S-H gel (Left alignment: Silicate sites after hydration; Center alignment: Silicate sites from raw materials; Right alignment: MCL and Al-Si sub.).

Si site	Ref		W2.5		W5		W7.5		W15	
	Pos.	Inter.	Pos.	Inter.	Pos.	Inter.	Pos.	Inter.	Pos.	Inter.
Q ⁴			-103	1.2	-105	1.7	-107.3	0.0	-107.3	1.5
Q ⁴ (1Al)			-100.8	0.1	-100.8	0.0	-100.8	0.1	-100.8	1.8
Q ³			-98.5	0.7	-99.7	0.7	-98.4	1.1	-98.4	0.3
Q ³ (1Al)			-93	0.2	-94.8	1.2	-94.8	0.6	-94.8	10.9
Q ³	-84.1	3.6								
Q ²	-81.9	11.8	-82.8	8.1	-82.8	0.0	-82.8	5.9	-82.8	9.0
Q ² (1Al)	-79.4	11.5	-79.4	25.2	-79.4	37.6	-79.4	18.6	-79.4	7.6
Q ¹	-78.6	31.8	-78.6	25.9	-78.6	15.2	-78.6	23.6	-78.6	30.6
Q ⁴ (W)*			-102.5	0.0	-102.5	0.5	-102.5	1.0	-102.5	0.0
Q ³ (W)			-95.8	0.2	-97.2	0.5	-97.2	0.3	-97.2	0.0
Q ² (W)			-90.9	0.0	-90.9	0.3	-90.9	0.0	-90.9	0.1
Q ¹ (W)			-84.2	11.5	-84.2	18.8	-84.2	12.4	-84.2	23.5
Q ⁰ (C)*	-72.8	22.5	-72.8	5.5	-72.8	6.7	-72.8	18.4	-72.8	3.4
Q ⁰ (C)	-71.2	16.4	-70.9	12.9	-71	11.6	-71	10.7	-70.8	9.1
Q ⁰ (C)	-69	2.3	-69	8.4	-69	5.1	-69	7.4	-69	2.3
MCL _{nc} **		3.8		4.9		7.0		4.3		3.4
MCL _c **		7.4		9.3		14.7		8.5		9.1
Al-Si sub.**		0.104		0.213		0.356		0.193		0.081

*(W) = From WTBW.

*(C) = From cement.

**MCL_{nc} = Mean chain length (non-crosslinked C-(A)-S-H structure).

**MCL_c = Mean chain length (crosslinked C-(A)-S-H structure).

Al-Si sub. = Al-Si substitution.

reaction potential in highly alkaline conditions.

Fig. 11 and Table 7 present the ²⁷Al MAS NMR results of cementitious systems incorporating WTBW at different replacement levels. The left alignment number is the aluminite sites after hydration, and the center alignment number is the aluminite sites from raw materials in Table 7. Fig. 12 shows the summary of silicate site changes from hydration products. The spectral deconvolution reveals significant changes in aluminum coordination environments as WTBW content increases, indicating interactions between WTBW-derived Al species and the cementitious matrix.

In the reference sample, the dominant signals correspond to Al(IV)-2 (82.5 ppm) and Al(IV)-1 (50.2 ppm) from cement, as well as Al(VI)-1 (10.9 ppm), which is associated with octahedral coordination in the unreacted clinker phases. Additionally, the presence of q² and q³ peaks suggests a degree of aluminosilicate network formation.

With WTBW incorporation, several shifts in the Al environment are observed. The intensity of Al(IV)-2 and Al(IV)-1 from cement decreases,

Fig. 8. ^{29}Si MAS NMR of paste samples at 28 days (a) Ref; (b) W2.5; (c) W5; (d)W7.5; (e)W15.

Fig. 9. Summary of Si sites for the hydration products (a–e), the changes in MCL and Al-Si substitution (f).

Fig. 10. ²⁷Al MAS NMR of raw materials (a) cement; (b) WTBW.

Table 6
²⁷Al MAS NMR of raw materials.

Al site	Cement		WTBW	
	Pos.	Inter.	Pos.	Inter.
Al(IV)-2	82.5	41.7		
Al(IV)-1	50.2	24.0		
Al(VI)-1	10.9	34.3		
Al(IV)-4			88	3.5
Al(IV)-3			57.6	71.8
Al(V)-1			26.5	21.1
Al(VI)-2			11.8	3.6

especially in W2.5 and W5, suggesting a dilution effect or reduced availability of these sites due to interactions with WTBW-derived phases. In contrast, the Al(IV)-3 site from WTBW (57.6 ppm) becomes increasingly prominent, particularly in W7.5 and W15, indicating

partial dissolution of WTBW aluminosilicates and their integration into the cementitious matrix. A similar trend is observed for Al(V)-1 (26.5 ppm), which is absent in lower WTBW contents but appears in W7.5 and W15, suggesting structural reorganization. The Al(VI) environment also shifts with WTBW addition. While the Al(VI)-1 site from cement remains relatively stable, Al(VI)-2 from WTBW (11.8 ppm) appears in W5 and decreases at higher WTBW contents, possibly due to its consumption during hydration reactions. The formation of additional Z[II] signals at lower chemical shifts (16, 15, and 14.5 ppm) in W2.5–W7.5 suggests secondary aluminosilicate phases, potentially linked to C–(A)–S–H or other gel structures.

These results indicate that aluminum from WTBW actively participates in the reaction process, altering the gel structure by introducing new Al(IV), Al(V), and Al(VI) sites. The higher intensity of Al(IV)-3 in W7.5 and W15 suggests enhanced aluminosilicate interactions at elevated WTBW contents, which could influence the long-term stability and mechanical performance of the system.

Fig. 11. ²⁷Al MAS NMR of paste samples at 28 days (a) Ref; (b) W2.5; (c) W5; (d)W7.5; (e)W15.

3.5. Microstructure

The microstructure of paste samples was investigated by performing XCT. Representative orthoslices for each sample subjected to X-ray imaging are shown on Fig. 13. The original data was equally cropped around the edges to reduce computational cost and eliminate the potential effect of present edge noise artefacts on phase segmentation. After the post-cropping process, the acquired datasets were converted to

8-bit, and the corresponding histogram grayscale range was normalized accordingly. The resulting volumes were identical for all the specimens.

It is worth noting that during visual inspection of the acquired datasets, long cracks were observed to have formed at the top and the bottom part of the reference paste specimen. No cracks were observed in any of the remaining samples, which all contained different amounts of WTBW powder. Characteristic 2D and 3D views can be observed in Fig. 14.

Table 7

²⁷Al MAS NMR of paste samples. (Left alignment: Aluminate sites after hydration; Center alignment: Aluminate sites from raw materials).

Al site	Position	Ref	W2.5	W5	W7.5	W15
q2(II)	79	16.5	0.1	0.5	0.5	1.1
q2(I)	75	1.4	21.2	20.5	12.2	8.2
q3(II)	47	20.1	0.8	1.7	2.3	2.3
q3(I)	43	2.2	20.5	18.6	9.6	10.4
Z(II)	16	40.6	-	-	-	-
Z(III)	15	-	-	-	-	7.6
Z(III)	14.5	-	3.9	6.5	7.4	-
Al (IV)-4 (W)	88	0.3	0.0	0.2	11.2	0.3
Al (IV)-2 (C)	82.5	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1
Al (IV)-3 (W)	57.6	1.0	10.2	11.8	25.7	36.6
Al (IV)-1 (C)	50.2	4.6	0.0	0.1	0.2	3.8
Al (V)-1 (W)	26.5	2.3	0.0	0.0	7.5	4.5
Al (VI)-2 (W)	11.8	-	-	28.7	13.3	4.6
Al (VI)-2 (W)	11.1	-	11.0	-	-	-
Al (VI)-1 (C)	10.9	10.5	32.3	11.3	10.1	20.6

After the post-phase segmentation, a quantitative analysis of the porosity behavior was performed. The corresponding 3D spatial distribution is given for each specimen in Fig. 15. A wide range of pore/void sizes can be observed all around the inspected volumes. The cumulative pore/void volume can be observed in Fig. 16. The pore volume distribution histogram reveals considerable differences in the porosity behavior among the samples investigated. Both reference and W5 specimens exhibit higher cumulative pore volume at the range of small pores/voids ($<10^{-2} \text{ mm}^3$), while no large pores/voids ($>1 \text{ mm}^3$) were detected. On the contrary, specimens W2.5, W7.5 and W15 exhibited a limited cumulative volume of small pores, while voids greater than 1 mm^3 were observed in all three specimens. Summing up the total volume of the segmented pores and voids for each sample yields interesting remarks. The minimum cumulative pore/void volume is spotted for the reference sample, while beyond that an almost linear growth of total volume is observed as the replacement percentage rises from 0 to 7.5 %. The trend is reversed in the case of W15, which indicates a significantly lower cumulative pore/void volume than the rest of the WTBW powder-containing samples.

The sample fabrication protocol was strictly identical, reducing the

possibility of attributing microstructural differences between samples to the preparation process, i.e. vibration time and mixing sequence. The amount of water present within the relevant mix designs remained constant, leading to a corresponding decrease in the w/c ratio as WTBW powder was added to partially replace cement. It is expected that the reduction in the amount of cement accelerated its full hydration with the extra water not being absorbed, and thus, creating air voids during the mix drying process. The limited amount of WTBW powder present in specimens W2.5, W5, and W7.5 was not sufficient to act as filler on the air voids forming during paste setting. In case of W15, it is expected that WTBW serves a dual role in substantially reducing the cumulative porosity. Firstly, the amount of powder within the mix is adequate to facilitate a filler effect. In addition, it is highly probable that the increased amount of WTBW powder could enhance its pozzolanic activity, facilitating hydration reactions with water and thus minimizing the amount of non-absorbed water surplus, ultimately reducing the cumulative air voids volume. Spatial distribution of porosity/air voids across the sample height is given in Fig. 17.

The distribution is relatively homogenous, both between the samples and across their height, with the only exception being the most porous specimen W7.5, which exhibits a consistently higher 2D porosity on the upper middle of the specimen. The uniform spatial distribution of porosity across the sample height is also indicative of the consistency followed on the preparation process. The pore/void shape was also investigated as a crucial parameter that can dominate the composite strength and durability [59,60]. It has been reported that non-spherical pores/voids can cause elevated stress zones while loading within the composite, leading to premature cracking and failure. The pore/void shape is classified among discoid, spheroid, blade, and rod based on shape factor, which is determined after calculating the flatness and elongation index [61]. If the 3D space occupied by a single pore/void is divided into a three-axis system x, y, and z, whose corresponding lengths are $l_x > l_y > l_z$, then the elongation index and flatness index are calculated as l_z/l_y and l_y/l_x , respectively. A Zingg diagram is then formulated, with the flatness index set at the x-axis, the elongation index set at the y-axis, and distinction lines are placed at 0.67. A Zingg diagram, composed for the results collected based on the XCT datasets, is illustrated in Fig. 18. The corresponding cumulative distribution of shape factor is shown in Fig. 19. Considerable variations can be observed

Fig. 12. Summary of Al sites for the hydration products.

Fig. 13. Illustration of (a) characteristic 2D views of the tomograms acquired for the five samples subjected to X-ray imaging; (b) phase segmentation protocol followed to isolate pore volume, including a characteristic line scan example.

among the five systems investigated. Based on the analysis performed, the least common pore/void shapes are disc and rod type (less than 20 % in all cases), while the majority of pores/voids are spherical and blade-type. It is worth noting that the reference specimen contains almost equal number of spherical and blade-type pores, while the trend is different in all cases where cement has been partially replaced by WTBW. In specimens W2.5, W7.5, and W15, spherical pores considerably outnumber blade-type pores/voids, while the trend is reversed in specimen W5.

3.6. Compressive strength

Fig. 20(a) shows the 28-day compressive strength of pastes with different replacement levels of WTBW powder and the fitting curve between strength and WTBW dosage. The compressive strength of the samples decreases progressively as the proportion of WTBW increases in the mixture.

The Reference sample reached 55.37 MPa, while the addition of 2.5 wt% WTBW significantly improved strength to 65.12 MPa, indicating that limited incorporation of WTBW promoted hydration with more C-S-H and CH formed and densified the microstructure. However, further increases in WTBW content led to a gradual decline in strength, falling to 51.49 MPa, 51.07 MPa, and 46.37 MPa at 5, 7.5, and 15 wt%, respectively. This suggests that excessive resin residues and reduced effective alkalinity begin to inhibit the hydration reactions and microstructural development beyond a certain threshold. Further discussion is presented in Section 4.3.

Fig. 20(b) illustrates the relationship between compressive strength

and hydration parameters, including the time to the reaction peak (TTRP) and the normalized height of the peak (HOP). The TTRP shows a negative correlation with strength, following the linear equation $y = 17.78 - 0.096x$ with an $R^2 = 0.70$. This shows that samples with higher strength reach their hydration peak earlier, indicating faster reaction kinetics. Conversely, the HOP demonstrates a positive correlation with strength, with a fitting equation $y = 0.0005 + 0.00001x$ and an $R^2 = 0.86$, indicating that mixtures with higher hydration peak intensity generally achieve higher compressive strength. These results feature that the incorporation of WTBW affects both hydration kinetics and mechanical properties, with higher replacement levels leading to delayed hydration and reduced strength.

4. Discussion

4.1. Dissolution of polyester resin-reinforced WTBW

The dissolution behavior of WTBW in an alkaline environment is influenced by the competition between its two main components: polyester resin and glass content. As shown in Fig. 21, both components interact with hydroxide ions (OH^-) in the pore solution, but their effects on cement hydration differ significantly.

Polyester resin primarily undergoes hydrolysis, breaking down into glycol and carboxylate salts. The initial WTBW spectrum shows a strong $\text{C}=\text{O}$ peak at 1712 cm^{-1} , indicative of ester groups in polyester resin. After exposure to an alkaline solution, the intensity of this peak decreases, while new peaks associated with glycol group (OH and $\text{C}-\text{H}$) and carboxylate group (COO^-) appear [62]. This chemical reaction

Fig. 14. Characteristic 2D views illustrating an extended crack network formed within the reference specimen volume 28 days after sample preparation (a) Characteristic 2D views on XZ plane (crack visualization); (b) Characteristic 2D views on XY plane (crack visualization); (c) Representative 3D views of the cracked reference specimen.

Fig. 15. Representative 3D views of porosity/air void spatial distribution for the five mortar specimens subjected to X-ray imaging.

process was also proven by Ismail et al. [20] through FTIR spectra, which revealed a decrease in the intensity of carboxylate anion and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ bands after hydration. This was due to the formation of ionic bonds between Ca^{2+} ions—produced from the hydrated calcium silicate in the hardened cement—and the carboxylate anions (COO^-) from the ester of the unsaturated polyester resin. This process consumes OH^- , leading to a local reduction in alkalinity, which may hinder the dissolution of other reactive phases in the system. The depletion of OH^- by polyester resin at an early age could slow down the initial hydration reactions of cement, particularly the dissolution of aluminates and silicate phases.

In contrast, the glass content of WTBW has a different impact. The dissolution of silicate and aluminate species from the glass network contributes to the long-term reaction process, releasing $\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$ and $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_4$ species into the pore solution. These species can participate in the formation of calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H) and aluminosilicate (C-A-S-H) gels, which enhance the microstructure of the hardened matrix. However, the competition for OH^- between polyester resin and glass content means that the dissolution of silicate phases may be delayed if the resin consumes a significant amount of alkalinity early on. Importantly, the dissolution of $\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$ and $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_4$ species from the glass content continues even at a very late hydration stage, further

Fig. 16. Illustration of (a) pore volume distribution; (b) cumulative pore volume for the five specimens investigated.

Fig. 17. Distribution of 2D porosity area fraction across the sample height.

contributing to the long-term development of the cementitious matrix. WTBW has potential as a SCM, its influence on cement hydration depends on the balance between organic and inorganic dissolution. The early-stage consumption of OH^- by polyester resin may slow down hydration, but the long-term release of reactive silicate and aluminate species from the glass content could still enhance the cementitious matrix over time.

4.2. Effect of WTBW on the formation of amorphous gels

The incorporation of WTBW into the cementitious system

significantly influences the structure of calcium (alumino)-silicate hydrate (C-(A)-S-H) gels. As illustrated in Fig. 22, when WTBW replacement increases up to 5 wt%, the gel structure becomes more three-dimensional due to higher Al-Si substitution. This is attributed to the increased availability of dissolved species, including Ca^{2+} , $\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$, and $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_4$, which are released from the glass phase of WTBW. The presence of crosslinked Al(IV) species promotes the formation of Q^3 Si units, leading to longer main chain lengths and a denser gel network.

However, when the WTBW replacement exceeds 5 wt%, a different trend occurs. The polyester resin component of WTBW begins to hinder the hydration process by consuming hydroxide ions and limiting the dissolution of reactive silicate and aluminate species. This results in a reduction of Al-Si crosslinking, leading to shorter gel chain lengths and a less connected network. As shown in Fig. 22, the gel structure transitions from a highly crosslinked 3D framework to a more fragmented structure, indicating a decline in overall gel polymerization. This suggests that excessive WTBW replacement may compromise the development of the cementitious matrix due to the adverse effects of polyester resin on hydration kinetics. The dual role of WTBW in the hydration process is revealed. While the glass content contributes beneficially by supplying reactive species that enhance the gel structure, the organic fraction of WTBW can negatively impact hydration when present in excess. Therefore, optimizing the WTBW replacement level is crucial to balancing these effects and maximizing the potential of WTBW as a SCM in cementitious systems.

4.3. Effect of WTBW on the microstructure and mechanical performance

The pore structure of the cementitious matrix is closely linked to the development and organization of the C-(A)-S-H gel network, as shown in Fig. 23, the correlation plot between pore type and MCL (only blade and sphere type remained as they are dominated pore types). At WTBW replacement levels up to 5 wt%, the system exhibits a denser and more cross-linked gel structure, which is reflected by the higher values of both MCL_n and MCL_{nc} from NMR data. This structural refinement appears to directly influence the type of pores formed within the matrix. Specifically, stronger and more complex gel structures tend to promote the formation of blade-type pores rather than spherical ones. These blade-like voids suggest that the extended and interconnected gel chains actively shape the pore geometry, occupying space in a directional and constrained manner rather than allowing uniform, isotropic pore

Fig. 18. Zingg diagram illustrating the pore/void shape classification for the five systems subjected to X-ray imaging.

Fig. 19. Pore morphology/shape factor distribution for the five systems subjected to X-ray imaging.

development. Shortly, the longer the MCL, the more blade-like the voids formed.

This phenomenon also points to a chemical and physical balance within the matrix. At WTBW content below 5 wt%, the reactive contribution from the waste particles might not be sufficient to significantly alter gel morphology or influence the development of more structured pore shapes. On the other hand, when the replacement exceeds 5 wt%, the presence of polyester resin and excessive filler content could hinder both the chemical hydration process and the physical continuity of the gel network. The inhibition of gel chain extension due to resin interference and possible dilution of cementitious reactants may lead to the formation of more spherical, less structured pores, as indicated by the negative correlation between MCL and sphere-type pores. The strongest

gel structure, formed at an optimal 5 wt% WTBW replacement, not only improves the 3D network connectivity but also modifies the internal pore architecture toward more elongated forms, enhancing the mechanical integrity and durability potential of the composite system.

When WTBW is incorporated into the cement system, the pore morphology evolves alongside changes in the gel structure. At replacement levels below 5 wt%, spherical pores tend to transform into blade-type pores, which are associated with an extended and interconnected C-(A)-S-H network. Although blade-type pores generally exhibit higher local stress concentrations than spherical ones due to their elongated geometry [63], they are effectively reinforced by the stronger three-dimensional gel framework [64], as evidenced by the increased MCL from the NMR results. This enhanced gel connectivity compensates

Fig. 20. (a) Compressive strength at 28 days and fitting with WTBW replacement level; (b) Fittings between compressive strength and TTPR or HOP.

for the potential stress concentration, resulting in improved compressive strength compared to the reference sample. However, when the WTBW replacement exceeds 5 wt%, the inhibitory effect of the polyester resin becomes more obvious, hindering the hydration process and limiting the formation of the C-(A)-S-H gel. Consequently, larger spherical pores form and the overall pore volume increases, leading to a noticeable decline in the mechanical strength of the composites at higher WTBW contents.

5. Conclusions

This study utilizes wind turbine blade waste (WTBW) as a partial replacement for cement to investigate its effects on the hydration process, microstructure, and gel structure of cementitious materials. Results show that the polyester resin component of WTBW reduces the alkalinity of the pore solution, which inhibits early-age hydration, while the glass content also consumes hydroxide ions but contributes beneficially by releasing silicate and aluminate monomers or dimers that promote gel formation. This highlights a competitive interaction between the

Polyester resin reinforced WTBW dissolution under alkaline environment

Fig. 21. Dissolution of polyester resin-reinforced WTBW under an alkaline environment.

Fig. 22. Effect of WTBW replacement on gel structure.

organic and inorganic phases of WTBW under alkaline conditions. The present results enhance the understanding of how WTBW influences cement hydration, microstructural development, and gelation behavior. Based on the findings, the following conclusions can be drawn.

- The dissolution of WTBW in an alkaline environment involves both organic and inorganic components. The polyester resin, as the organic part, consumes hydroxide ions and releases glycol and carboxylate salts, which hinders the early hydration process. In contrast, the glass content, as the inorganic part, also consumes alkalinity but releases additional Si(OH)₄ and Al(OH)₄ species that support gel formation and hydration. This positive effect from the glass may compensate for the negative impact of the resin, contributing to improved long-term performance.
- The Si NMR results of WTBW indicate a high proportion of Q³ and Q⁴ silicate species in the glass content, while Al NMR analysis reveals the presence of Al(IV), Al(V), and Al(VI) coordination environments. These findings support the incorporation of both silicate and

aluminate species from the glass phase into the gel structure, contributing to the formation of a more three-dimensional and longer-chain C-(A)-S-H gel network. This structural enhancement is most pronounced at around 5 wt% WTBW replacement. Beyond this level, the inhibitory effect of the polyester resin becomes dominant, reducing the mean chain length of both cross-linked and non-cross-linked gels.

- The pore structure evolution is closely linked to the development of C-(A)-S-H gels. At 5 wt% WTBW replacement, the formation of longer and more interconnected gel chains promotes blade-type pores due to spatial constraints imposed by the 3D gel network. Below 5 wt%, the gel growth is limited by insufficient reactive contribution, while above 5 wt%, the excessive resin content hinders gel continuity, leading to more spherical and less structured pores.

WTBW offers measurable benefits in paste formulations when finely milled and used as an SCM. These benefits suggest broader applicability across building materials, such as improved microstructural refinement

Fig. 23. Effect of WTBW replacement on pore structure.

and acceptable compressive performance at low replacement levels. Beyond paste, WTBW has potential in other cement-based products such as render mortars (which our research is going on), lightweight concrete units [65], façade panels [66], and even prefabricated components [7], where high structural loads are not critical. Furthermore, WTBW has the potential for multipurpose use in various cement-based products, like fiber reinforcement [7,10,67] or partially replacing aggregates in concrete. For building designers, especially architects, this presents a practical opportunity to incorporate circular economy strategies into material selection [66,68,69]. By specifying materials that integrate recycled composite waste, designers can reduce the environmental footprint of buildings while supporting innovation in sustainable material systems without compromising performance or constructability, which could be of scientific and practical interest in future study [2,70].

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Tao Liu: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ceren Duyal:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Charilaos Paraskevoulakos:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Kasper Enemark-Rasmussen:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Ashal Tyurkay:** Writing – review & editing. **Nataliya Lushnikova:** Writing – review & editing. **Florent Gauvin:** Writing – review & editing. **Ana Teresa Lima:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgment

This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement no. 101096437. Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible.

This work was also supported by Aase og Ejnar Danielsens Fond

under grant agreement no. 24-30-0101.

During the preparation of this work, the authors used Gemini in order to improve readability, grammar, and language. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and took full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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